

Abstract

Digital Chinese Medicine and High-Tech Acupuncture: Integrating Chinese and Western Medicine.

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Abstract

This opening keynote lecture explores the integration of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) with modern technological advancements, leading to the development of Digital Chinese Medicine (DCM) and High-Tech Acupuncture. It highlights key innovations and international collaborations between Switzerland, Austria, China, and beyond.

An introduction to DCM sets the foundation by discussing its evolution and applications in Europe and China. A short overview of high-tech acupuncture provides insights into selected content and advancements.

Key technological breakthroughs are examined, including robot-assisted acupuncture, which utilizes automation for precision treatment (cooperation with Nanjing, Taichung). Furthermore, computer-controlled laser acupuncture (cooperation with Taichung) is analyzed for its potential in non-invasive stimulation methods. The lecture also explores teleacupuncture, a cutting-edge approach enabling remote treatments across multiple locations, such as Graz, Bad Zurzach, Beijing, Wuhan, Harbin, and Shanghai.

The opening keynote concludes with an analysis of future prospects, discussing the potential for further integration of digital tools in acupuncture and traditional medicine. These advancements mark a significant step toward a more globally connected and technologically enhanced approach to integrative medicine.

Keywords: Digital Chinese Medicine; High-Tech Acupuncture; Integrative Medicine.

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